

“I Will Surviva!” Key Insights from the Postgraduate Research Student’s Experience of the Confirmation Viva.

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Abstract

This paper explores the processes involved in completing the Confirmation Viva, which is a written and oral examination of postgraduate research within 12 – 21 months of registration on PhD-track in Dublin City University’s Institute of Education (DCU IoE). It is a formal registry process for transferring from PhD-track to PhD register, and shares similarities with the Transfer Viva, moving from Masters by Research to PhD register. The Confirmation Viva signifies an opportunity to defend the research conducted to-date and to establish if it will merit an eventual PhD award. This paper explores key insights that emerged before, during and after the Confirmation Viva process for one full-time postgraduate researcher, namely; preparation for examination, the experience of examination, and progress post-examination. Having reflected on its positive outcome, this paper provides an insight on how to ‘survive’ the Confirmation Viva and concludes that such processes might be replicable in preparation for the Viva Voce in time to come.

Key Words

Confirmation Viva; Registry; Examination; Postgraduate Research Student; Professional Development.

Three Main Highlights

The Confirmation Viva is a:

- unique and important opportunity to defend research in the early stages of postgraduate research studies
- valuable experience to discuss the proposed research topic in detail to identify any gaps in the study content, design or intended outputs
- form of professional growth for the postgraduate researcher to support both research project progression and personal development

Experiences of Participation

Reflection on the oral examination of the Confirmation Viva might be guided by its duration, location, satisfaction with examiner, thesis outcome, and overall satisfaction with its facilitation (Share, 2016). In terms of duration, the initial 10-minute oral presentation offered comfort and secured a predictable opening trajectory to ‘settle’ into the examination. As well as this, the 60-minute oral examination that ensued offered a supportive environment for critical discussion, which not only contributed a high-level of satisfaction with the examiner, but also with the ‘fairness’ of the process (Davis and Engward, 2018). Researchers caution that academic argument might be complicated by contrasting views between the examiner and examinee (ibid). However, in this instance, a prevailing respect among all parties, coupled with an effective Chair, ensured that there were no power relations issues as previously cited in the literature. The online forum for examination enabled a relatively hassle-free experience, with no need to travel to or from site and no need to acclimatise to an unfamiliar environment when on site. When it was time for the student to leave the virtual meeting so that the examiners could convene, a feeling of exhaustion arose, as it had required

a lot of thought and energy to defend the research up to that point. However, upon clarification of recommendation for confirmation to PhD register, there was a strong feeling of relief and elation that outweighed this tiredness. A short discussion followed, with recommendations for progressing the research, which were teased out where necessary so as to provide a valuable learning experience for the scholar. The entire experience was positive, with ample opportunities for growth in both the research project, but also in the student's approach to preparing for, and participating in, the eventual Viva Voce.

Introduction

According to the *Academic Regulations for Postgraduate Degrees by Research and Thesis*, any PhD-track student of DCU must “*undergo a confirmation procedure*” (DCU, 2018, p. 16). The purpose of this ‘confirmation’ is to establish satisfactory student progress and to explore whether the proposed research topic will merit an eventual PhD award (ibid). An internal examiner, endorsed by the Head of School, together with the primary supervisor, subject the postgraduate research student to a written and oral examination of their work to-date, and then submit a written report of the outcome of these assessments to the Graduate Research Studies Board (GRSB). This results in either confirmation to the PhD register, a recommendation for graduation with a Master's degree, or in exceptional circumstances, re-application for confirmation at a later stage in the study (ibid).

This article presents one research scholar's experience of preparing for, participating in, and learning from the Confirmation Viva, which resulted in confirmation to the PhD register. It begins with an exploration of the literature surrounding postgraduate research studies, postgraduate researcher professional development and findings relating to Viva Voce experiences. It progresses with a narrative account of the steps that were involved in

preparing for, participating in, and progressing from the Confirmation Viva. It then discusses key outcomes for future postgraduate research scholars of DCU to consider when preparing for the Confirmation Viva. It concludes with a summary which outlines how aspects of the Confirmation Viva experience might contribute to the eventual Viva Voce.

Literature Review

This paper explores literature relating to three core areas that are applicable to the Confirmation Viva: postgraduate research studies, postgraduate researcher professional development, and Viva Voce experiences. Key search terms for this review included Ireland; education; experiences; postgraduate research; professional development; Viva Voce; examination. Summon and EBSCO were the primary search engines used for these terms.

Postgraduate Research Studies

The PhD process has many “*pitfalls and perils to overcome or avoid*” (Almeida-Souza and Baets, 2012, p. 189), necessitating knowledge of such risks, to enable a more successful experience of postgraduate research studies. A literature search on these challenges outlines three core essentials to achieve this goal: research supervision, a confident and capable scholar, and research cultures within institutions.

A quantitative, survey-based study of 123 postgraduate research students in management programmes in Malaysia outlines crucial factors that influence their performance (Ul Hadi and Muhammad, 2019), with supervision, and more specifically supervisors, having a statistically significant influence on the performance of their postgraduate researchers. Therefore, supervision plays a central role in the postgraduate research process. Of note here, however, is the fact that “*postgraduate research supervision*

occurs within a rapidly changing environment” (McCallin and Nayar, 2012, p. 71), which necessitates formal and frequent training for supervision. It could be argued that the Confirmation Viva is one such opportunity for the supervisory panel to familiarise with regulatory processes of their relevant institutions, while also upskilling in the area of examination and student support, which enables the supervisor to react and adapt to the ever-evolving demands of the role.

Ul Hadi and Muhammad (2019) also establish that more capable and confident postgraduate research students are more able to conduct their research independently, thereby exemplifying the importance of providing opportunities for the student to establish capability for, and confidence with, research processes. This correlates with Almeida-Souza and Bates (2012), who advocate that though supervisory input is an important source of ideas and advice, the scholar’s own growing expertise and subject knowledge ought to emerge more prominently as the research progresses. The Confirmation Viva provides the platform for postgraduate researchers of DCU to demonstrate that they are capable of collating a logical, coherent narrative of their early research, and to also develop their confidence in defending that collection of work through an oral examination.

Academic institutions, such as DCU, are encouraged to recognise the importance of a *“strong research culture for postgraduate research students’ performance”* (Ul Hadi and Muhammad, 2019, p. 68). This is further compounded by McCallin and Nayar (2012), who advocate for support systems that can contribute to the growth and development of research scholars. DCU IoE has borne this legacy in its introduction of Research in Progress Seminars, and an annual Postgraduate Researcher’s Unconference, which coincide with Research Methods Modules, to provide a holistic support structure for postgraduate researchers. The connections and supports gleaned from such initiatives ensure that every postgraduate

researcher has the option of tapping into a strong research culture to enhance their own capability and confidence for research.

The Confirmation Viva enables the intersection of all three central components of postgraduate research studies:

- supervision as a supportive, though critical, source for exploration of research to-date,
- a confident, capable research student through the submission of a written account of research-to date, and through the oral defence of that work,
- and a research culture that supports students' growth and development.

With regard to postgraduate research studies, the Confirmation Viva provides essential opportunities for both macro- and micro-level research processes that are imperative to the success of the research scholar. This necessitates an exploration of professional development for postgraduate research to contribute to such success.

Postgraduate Researcher Professional Development

DCU offers a comprehensive *Postgraduate Researcher Development Framework* to develop postgraduate students' skills, not only for independent research, but also for transferability to other employment settings (DCU, 2021a). The *Postgraduate Researcher Development Framework* is underpinned by “*best international practice in the field of Postgraduate Degree research and the Irish Universities Association's PhD Graduates' Skills*” (ibid, p.2), which instils an undeniable trustworthiness and reliability in its adoption for professional growth. The framework presents four key skills, including: research skills, personal effectiveness, communication for impact and career progression. These are further broken down into measurable competencies (see p. 3 – 6) which provide valuable guidance for self-driven professional development as part of the postgraduate research journey in

DCU. Upon closer examination, one might argue that the Confirmation Viva offers a key platform for the development of these four skills. For example:

- *research skills* are further developed in the area of theoretical knowledge, methods and ethical practice (ibid, p. 3),
- *personal effectiveness* is enhanced through the skill of project management, in this case, the project was the compilation of a ‘Confirmation Thesis’ (ibid, p. 4),
- *communication for impact* examples might include writing this thesis, and indeed, providing a synopsis oral presentation of such in the opening minutes of the Confirmation Viva oral examination (ibid, p. 5), and,
- *career progression* is supported by expanding on the research scholar’s network, not only by becoming acquainted with the examiner, but also by conveying the experience with other postgraduate researchers (ibid, p. 6).

It is conceivable, therefore, that the Confirmation Viva presents an important professional development opportunity for the postgraduate research scholar. While research on both postgraduate research studies and professional development for such studies establishes some context for this paper, it is literature on the Viva Voce process itself that provides an important backdrop for anticipating potential Confirmation Viva experiences.

Viva Voce Experiences

Davis and Engward (2018) explored the experiences of eighteen participants, who had undergone an examination of their doctoral research in the United Kingdom between 2013 – 2018, through the use of semi-structured interviews. Motivation for this study stemmed from the predominant focus on the Viva Voce as “*a process to be prepared for, as opposed to an experience that is lived by the candidate*” (ibid, p. 31). Key topics that emerged from the

thematic analysis of these interviews with doctoral researchers included: academic argument, emotions, fairness and practical issues. Academic argument, though desired by candidates, was not always facilitated, particularly where contrasting views prevailed between the examiner and the examinee, which poses one strong consideration for the Confirmation Viva. Davis and Engward (2018) also found that the Viva Voce is frequently an emotional experience, with anxiety and nervousness some of the more prominent emotions cited, and it is conceivable that such emotions might also prevail during the Confirmation Viva. Questionable fairness of examination arose at times due to a lack of regulations application, other times due to having an ineffective Chair, or sometimes due to the choice of examiner. This raises the question of fairness during the Confirmation Viva. Practical considerations in this study's findings included room type, light, ventilation and space, as well as the general atmosphere and reassurance created by the processes of welcome, provision of water etc. Such themes might underpin a framework for reflecting on the Confirmation Viva experience that is presented later in this paper.

Share (2016) examined the Viva Voce experiences of 87 social science PhD graduates from three Irish higher education institutions through a questionnaire. Respondents believed that the Viva Voce's purpose was for defence, authentication and examination of the research conducted. In preparation for the Viva Voce, supervisory advice was the most dominant source of support, with oral presentations at conferences or internal seminars, and reading books on doing a PhD, following closely after. To a lesser extent, mock vivas, advice from family members and viva workshop attendance were additional sources of preparation for the Viva Voce. Preparation for the Confirmation Viva might follow a similar trajectory. Respondents reported their experiences during the Viva Voce with regard to duration, location, satisfaction with examiner, thesis outcome, and overall satisfaction with how their

viva was conducted. These focal points offer a replicable opportunity for investigation of the Confirmation Viva experience. Share's (2016) study also establishes participants' experiences after the Viva Voce with regard to receiving the examiners' report, dealing with corrections, value of viva to thesis completion, emotions, and physical reactions. As with Davis and Engward's study, Share (2016) provides a roadmap for guiding a narrative of the Confirmation Viva experience, to ensure its depiction might correlate to the Viva Voce and add further to the conversation around this lesser established body of research.

The literature on postgraduate research studies, postgraduate researcher professional development and Viva Voce experiences provides valuable insights for preparation for, participation in and progress after the Confirmation Viva. Such knowledge influences perceptions of the Confirmation Viva as experienced by the author of this paper and informs the content hereafter on this formal registry process of DCU.

Confirmation Viva Process

This section of the paper presents the steps followed by one postgraduate researcher of DCU IoE in preparation for the Confirmation Viva. It also depicts the processes of examination as experienced from that scholar's perspective. Steps for progress beyond the Confirmation Viva are provided so as to present a coherent narrative of the steps involved before, during, and after this formal registry process of DCU.

For contextual purposes, it is worth noting that this Confirmation Viva was completed in month 25 of full-time postgraduate research in DCU. This exceeds the 21-month cut-off point, but was deemed acceptable by the Dean of Graduate Studies, due to uncontrollable circumstances that had prohibited its completion any sooner. Furthermore, the process of oral

examination was conducted online via Zoom, due to national measures to control the spread of COVID-19, which prohibited opportunities for on-site meetings at that point in time. Both factors significantly affected the processes that are depicted with regard to this experience in the following section.

Preparing for the Confirmation Viva

There were two key phases of preparation for the Confirmation Viva:

1. Preparing the written submission
2. Preparing for oral examination

The former stemmed over a three-month period, while the latter occurred over a four-week period following the submission of the written piece.

Consultation with the supervisory panel established practical procedures for the Confirmation Viva, namely: a potential date, location and examiner, the provision of an abstract for the examiner to consider before committing to examination, the required written submission (in this case, a ‘Confirmation Thesis’ was deemed appropriate), the preparation of a 10-minute oral presentation to use for the beginning of the oral examination, and the projected timeline for PhD completion.

Consultation with fellow research scholars further demystified the process of Confirmation Viva, and provided moral support for embracing its requirements of both written and oral examination.

Preparing the Written Submission

There are no official guidelines on the written content that might be submitted for the Confirmation Viva. The regulations recommend that a “*substantial body of work*” (DCU,

2018, p. 16) is submitted by the research student for both written and oral examination, but there is no further stipulation on what that work might look like. As the PhD research in question will strive towards a monograph thesis submission for the final Viva Voce, it was apt to pursue the submission of a ‘Confirmation Thesis’ for the Confirmation Viva. The contents of this thesis are detailed in table 1 below.

Table 1: An overview of the contents provided in the Confirmation Viva Thesis.

Confirmation Thesis Contents
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Abstract● Table of Contents● List of Tables, Figures & Abbreviations● Introduction● Selected Literature Review● Methodology● Data Analysis (Pilot Findings & Procedure for Main Study)● Timeline for Completion & Training Needs Analysis● Reference List● Appendices

It is important to acknowledge that this submission represented just over two years of postgraduate research work, and it is not prescriptive of what might be expected of a scholar completing the Confirmation Viva at an earlier stage in their research journey.

This ‘Confirmation Thesis’ was a product of cyclical drafts and consultations with the primary supervisor of the current study over a three-month period. These processes offered valuable opportunities to train for the compilation of the final thesis document, as they enabled the student to rationalise, summarise, and justify the research in iterative cycles. Furthermore, the overall study became clearer, with a predictable pathway emerging for eventual completion.

Submitting the Written Work

The ‘Confirmation Thesis’ was submitted via email to the examiner four weeks prior to the intended examination (see appendix 1 for an example of the accompanying email). Supervisory panel members were CC’d in the email. An acknowledgement of receipt and well wishes were returned from both the examiner and supervisory panel. The first phase of Confirmation Viva preparation was complete.

Preparing for the Oral Examination

Having submitted the written work, the author had four weeks to prepare for examination. It was helpful to:

- print a copy of the written submission to have as a reference to inform possible discussion points,
- prepare bullet pointed notes from each section of the submission,
- source sample Viva questions to inform potential questions / responses,
- ask a fellow research scholar to be a critical friend in discussing the work to-date and,
- exercise frequently and get plenty of rest.

The creation of a short PowerPoint presentation was a significant source of comfort and clarity in the days preceding the examination. It introduced the researcher’s background, the study context, rationale and opportunities, theoretical underpinnings of the project, the pilot study overview, the main study intentions and a projected timeline for completion.

The student felt nervous, anxious, though somewhat prepared, for the Confirmation Viva experience. While exercise was important for coping with the undesirable emotions that arose, so too was frequent and supportive contact with supervision, postgraduate peers and family. As well as this, rest was vital to ensure maximum performance on the day of the oral examination.

Participation in the Confirmation Viva

There was a predictable schedule of processes on the day of the Confirmation Viva (see table 2 below).

Table 2: A potential schedule for the Confirmation Viva

Confirmation Viva Schedule (Based on Personal Experience)	
1.	Welcome / Introductions
2.	Student Presentation
3.	Oral Examination (A Series of Questions)
4.	Student Break from Meeting while Examiners Convene
5.	Review with Advice for Study Progression & Next Steps
6.	Thanks / Conclusion

These were established by the primary supervisor in advance of the examination. Everyone present at the Confirmation Viva was reminded of this schedule when the examination began. Attendees included the student, examiner, primary supervisory and secondary supervisor. Further housekeeping measures involved ensuring student comfort with the process, with the option to take a break, if needed, at any stage, while the secondary supervisor opted to scribe the examination proceedings, to enable the student to reap the full value of the experience by reflecting on these notes afterwards.

The examination began with a 10-minute oral presentation by the student. It proceeded with questions from the examiner specific to the 'Confirmation Thesis' content, specifically with regard to context, literature, methodology and data analysis. The student found it helpful to note down key words from the question being asked to have as a reference point when answering that question. Thought provoking dialogue ensued, with a supportive atmosphere cultivated for critical discussion of the research work to-date. Some gaps emerged in the student's knowledge and prior thought, which afforded key considerations for the progression of the research. For example, much of the research work up to that point had focused on designing and developing a bilingual oral narrative programme called *Tell a Tale | Inis Scéal* for linguistically diverse junior primary classes, while less time had been devoted to establishing a teacher professional development framework for *Tell a Tale | Inis Scéal* delivery. The gap, and recommendation, was to revisit the literature on effective teacher professional development to maximise the potential of *Tell a Tale | Inis Scéal* implementation for language development in diverse settings. In line with the schedule, the student was then asked to leave the meeting, while the examiner and primary supervisor convened on the work that had been submitted and the conversation that had unfolded. Having returned minutes

later to hear the outcome of the process, the student's confidence and morale was boosted, thanks to a proposal for confirmation on the PhD register. Some recommendations were made for study progression, with ample opportunity to discuss and explore these to ensure full comprehension of how to proceed post-examination.

Progress after the Confirmation Viva

The examiner and primary supervisor prepared a report, outlining their critical evaluation of the written and oral submission. This report was sent to the student for review. It was read, signed and returned to the panel, so that it could then be presented to the Graduate Research Studies Board (GRSB). A notification letter was issued soon after to congratulate the student on the successful transfer to PhD register and to advise of corresponding changes to registration status. This necessitated a new student card and once issued, the 'confirmation' process was complete.

Discussion

There were many key learning points taken from the Confirmation Viva process. Drawing from the work of Share (2016), the Confirmation Viva is now discussed in terms of support for preparation, experiences of examination and processes post-examination. Davis and Engward (2018) also provide a framework for further elaboration on this discussion with regard to academic argument, fairness, emotions and practical components during examination, which are thus included in the unfolding commentary.

Support for Preparation

In line with Share's (2016) findings, this paper depicts supervisory input and guidance as a core support for examination preparation during the Confirmation Viva. However, unlike Share (2016), consultation with fellow research scholars, and indeed, critical discussion as a 'mock' Confirmation Viva with one such person, was the second most important source of support for preparation, in place of oral presentations and further reading, as cited in Share's study. This might be attributed to the strong research culture and community that exists within DCU (Ul Hadi and Muhammad, 2019), and the author's proactivity in accessing such support from colleagues.

Research posits that feelings of anxiety, fear and nerves prevail in the lead up to examination (Wellington, 2010; Davis and Engward, 2018). The oral examination, in particular, "*is often stressful and difficult to prepare for*" (Watts, 2012, p. 372), thereby cultivating a platform for uncertainty and worry. All of these emotions were felt prior to the oral examination component of the Confirmation Viva, which has accommodated a valuable opportunity for the author to learn to cope with the emotions of such examination processes at an academic level. Student well-being in the lead up to Viva Voce examination is less-established in the literature. However, research shows correlations between well-being and performance (Edgar *et al.*, 2015), which highlights the importance of including well-being strategies within preparation plans for both the Confirmation Viva and Viva Voce. The current study found that ongoing support from the supervisory panel, exercise, sleep and social encounters with college friends made important contributions to overall well-being prior to the Confirmation Viva.

Processes Post-Examination

There was a great sense of achievement upon receipt of the official Confirmation Viva report, otherwise known as the PGR-3 (DCU, 2021b), after the oral examination. All comments therein were a true reflection of the examiners' recommendations on the day of the Confirmation Viva, and were valuable in providing a framework to address any major gaps that had emerged from that discussion. There was a strong sense of 'fairness' in the examination process, which is inconsistent with the findings of Davis and Engward's study.

Though both the oral and written recommendations highlighted gaps in the study, they also offered advice to address such gaps, which not only contributed towards the student's capability for conducting research, but also their confidence in addressing such shortcomings. Furthermore, having been confirmed to the PhD register, the expectation is that the study might now merit an eventual PhD award (Hodgson, 2020), which greatly develops researcher capability and confidence, qualities that are vital in any PhD candidate for postgraduate success (Ul Hadi and Muhammad, 2019).

The final, prevailing outcome of the Confirmation Viva for the author of this paper was the term "*I will survive!*" What had once been an unthinkable, potentially insurmountable, attempt at research defence, was now an achievable and realistic target, given the fair, comprehensive and supportive experience of examination. Appendix 2 further elaborates on this belief with an obligatory sing-song mantra for the eventual Viva Voce process.

Conclusion

Despite its roots as a formal registry process, the Confirmation Viva offers a key opportunity for reflection, discussion and growth during one's PhD research journey in DCU

IoE. It offers the unique chance to defend the research conducted to-date, which is important to establish if the work is worth pursuing to merit an eventual PhD award (Hodgson, 2020). As well as this, the Confirmation Viva is a valuable experience to discuss the research conducted thus far in detail to identify any gaps in the study content, design or intended outputs. Finally, given its potential to confirm or deny one's status as a PhD scholar in DCU IoE, it is a key form of professional growth for the postgraduate researcher to boost both capability for, and confidence in, research (Ul Hadi and Muhammad, 2019), as well as contributing to other key competencies identified in the *Postgraduate Researcher Development Framework* (DCU, 2021a). Appendix 3 provides a handout with an overview of this experience and practical tips to consider ahead of engagement with the Confirmation Viva process.

In preparation for the final Viva Voce, future postgraduate scholars might consider the work of both Share (2016) and Davis and Engward (2018) when preparing for the *lived experience* of this examination, as opposed to focusing solely on the process of being examined. Preparation for the Viva Voce might include seeking clarity on practical procedures, such as choice of examiner, location of examination, clarification of primary supervisor as a potential Chair of proceedings, establishment of a schedule, familiarisation with the regulations surrounding examination etc. to ensure a fair opportunity for academic defence. Furthermore, well-being strategies such as exercise, rest and social contact might offer means to cope with the inevitable emotions that arise in advance of the oral examination. Finally, one might proceed with confidence in their capability to engage with the Viva Voce, after having emerged from the Confirmation Viva with the ability to “surviva”.

Funding Details

This work was supported by the DCU-INTO150 PhD scholarship.

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Appendix 1 – Sample E-mail for Written Submission

Dear _____

Please see attached my Confirmation Thesis for your review. I am also sending the corresponding appendices in a separate document to further illustrate parts of the Confirmation Thesis discussion.

I have included both PDF and word document versions of the Confirmation Thesis. I have included a PDF only of the appendices (word document was quite large) but I can forward the word document version too if the PDF version does not suffice. Let me know if you have any difficulty with accessing these and I will send them again.

Thank you in advance for the time you will give to examining my research to-date. I look forward to meeting you, Supervisor 1 & Supervisor 2 (CC'd here) on _____ to discuss this work.

Kind regards,

Appendix 2 – ‘I Will Surviva’ Song

*This song was part of an oral presentation at the
DCU IoE Postgraduate Research Unconference 2021*

At first I was afraid, I was petrified,
Kept thinking, if I try defend this research, I could die inside.
But then I spent so many nights researching ways my work belongs,
And I grew strong, and I learned how to get along...

And so I typed, and I embraced,
Research in a pandemic and meetings through cyberspace.
I could have thrown in the towel, I could have made it disappear, but
then, I knew I would regret it, if I didn't persevere.

So on I go, and I endure, I'm so strong now
'Cause I'm confirmed forever-more.
Aren't you the one with an educational need reply?
Will you crumble? Will you lay down and die?

Oh no, not I, I will surviva...
Oh, as long as I know how to research, I know I'll stay alive-ah,
I've got a lot of knowledge to give,
I've got a thesis to submit,
I will surviva... I will surviva... hey hey!

You are screen sharing

Stop Share

Talking:

I Will Surviva

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DCU IOE POSTGRADUATE RESEARCH UNCONFERENCE

Appendix 3 – Practical Tips for the Confirmation Viva

'I Will Surviva'

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Please note that these tips are based on one student's experience of the Confirmation Viva and are provided by that student as part of an oral presentation at the DCU IoE Postgraduate Research Unconference 2021

Preparation	Participation	Progress
<p><u>Preparation for Written Examination</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consult with your supervisory panel regarding expectations for the confirmation viva <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ content required for submission ○ potential examiner ○ due date for written submission ○ date of oral examination ○ timeline for PhD completion ○ training needs analysis ● Talk to fellow PhD scholars to establish their experiences, learn from their approaches and get moral support for the process ● Review the PGR-3 form which is accessible on the registry section of the DCU website ● draft, submit for feedback, re-draft, submit for feedback, re-draft and submit for examination <p><u>Preparation for Oral Examination</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Print a copy of the submission to have as a reference during discussion ● Prepare bullet pointed notes from each section of the submission ● Source sample Viva questions to inform potential question responses ● Ask a fellow research scholar to be a critical friend in discussing your work to-date ● Take lots of breaks and get plenty of sleep! 	<p><u>A Potential Schedule (Based on Personal Experience)</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Welcome / Introductions 2. Student Presentation 3. Oral Examination (A Series of Questions) 4. Student Break from Meeting while Examiners Convene 5. Review with Advice for Study Progression & Next Steps 6. Thanks / Conclusion <p><u>Tips for Participation</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enjoy your presentation as this is a predictable and affirmative part of the examination process ● Jot down key words from the question being asked to ensure you answer appropriately ● Take your time to reflect and consider before answering any questions ● If applicable, admit lack of previous thought on a specific matter ● Have a bottle of water nearby as you will do a LOT of talking 	<p><u>Next Steps</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Your examiner and primary supervisor prepare a report (PGR-3), outlining their critical evaluation of your written and oral submission. ● This report is sent to you for review. ● You read, sign and return to your panel. ● It then goes to the Graduate Research Studies Board (GRSB). They send a letter to notify you of any changes to your registration status. <p><u>Tips for Progress</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Review the report and create an action plan to fill the gaps in your research to-date based on the feedback given ● Critique your oral presentation skillset to identify needs for eventual Viva Voce ● Celebrate achieving this milestone on your PhD research journey ● Continue with confidence that 'You Will Surviva' when progressing towards the final stages of your PhD

